

Effect of teeth periodontium presence on the bone physiology against stiffer status after implant placement or teeth ankylosis event. Difference of teeth against dental implants a new pivotal concept in the biomechanics

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Mohammed Zahid Saadoon¹, David I Adam²

1 Ashty Teaching hospital
Erbil, Kurdistan region, Iraq
mzsmaxillofacial@gmail.com
2 OSTEOOTECH UK LIMITED
London – UK
davidibrahamadam@gmail.com

Abstract

Teeth had special attachment to the alveolar processes of the jaws. These unique anatomical domains considered by anatomists as a specialized joint. It had special molecular signaling. These attachments of the teeth provide unparalleled very well controlled in the term of its response. We want to demonstrate this response grossly and compare this response in a parametric way to the dental implants.

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of bone, jaws weakeners, jaw stiffeners.

Introduction

In our previously published paper, we had demonstrated clearly the effect of the PD passively on the alveolar process. (1) In this paper we will demonstrate the effect of

- 1- absence of PD ligament
- 2- nature of the tooth and titanium dental implants on the stress transfer from the tooth or implant to the alveolar bone

Methods

This model had been chosen based on our models in the previously published book (MOHAMMED BODIES' ANALYSIS FEA OF DENTAL IMPLANTS' DESIGN CRITERIA) (2)

Figure 1 This model represents the same geometry for implant and tooth

This model is very robust to represent the loads and strains distribution

Results and discussions

The success of an implant depends on many factors and to guarantee success, we should deal with these factors as a credit scoring system. The more positive points, the more guaranteed success

Figure 2 This is the displacement of model with better gradient of stiffness

The total displacement / bone displacement $\approx 7.7/0.6 \approx 12.8$

When choosing the higher modulus of elasticity (E) for the crown and lower E for the implant and abutment, we will get more bone displacement representing more deformity, which will be reflected by more remodeling which results in better survivability of the implant. In the case of the tooth model, the ratio is much lower between total displacement and displacement inside of the PD component of the tooth model.

Implant criteria of evaluation should not be retrieved directly from the tooth model, and by no means, the comparison should be done directly. Although we do the finite element analysis for solid and two pieces model, we have analyzed only the hollowed model here due to its intermediate deformability between them. PD component is not just a cushion tissue with a predominant fibrous component, but rather could be considered as a vascular compartment. Its mechanical properties is scarcely knowledged, and as the cartilage regarded softer, the bone PD regarded to the soft tissues softer. The debate about whether the PD principal fibers is under compression or tension when the tooth is loaded continue unresolved. This highly viscoelastic tissue must not be compared to the osseointegration. PD tissues are extremely complex to be remodeled inside of the FEA, although we modeled it as very soft plastic material with the Poisson ration of 0.3 with E of 1MPa. The highest turnover in all of the body osseous tissue is in the alveolar process of the maxilla and mandible, reflecting the high biomechanical demands of these areas

Figure 3 This is the bone displacement of model with better gradient of stiffness

The displacement here is higher than that of the other model, where the crown has lower E and abutment and implant have high E, so the gradient here is better to be chosen

Figure 4 This is the strain energy density of model with better gradient of stiffness

Maximum elastic strain energy here has 5 times greater highest value than in other models, while in the tooth model it is roughly 10 times greater. The Pattern of strain energy density, in case the implant has lower E, is more widely distributed reaching close to the core of implant, but not deeper as in case of the implant with higher E, in which the pattern is more superficial. In the case of the tooth model, strain energy density is encompassing the vast majority of the root. We admit that we didn't model the root canal in our tooth model because we think it had no significant effect on results. The modulus of elasticity of a tooth is ever-changing and it will be raised with age. Root canal treatment doesn't provide continuous repair to the tooth composite structure. Precipitation of intratubular and secondary or tertiary dentin

is not haphazardly processed, but it could depend on the mechanical demand of the tooth which is sensed by the complex pulp tissues. As the bone resorption process had unexposed many aspects up to these days, dental pulp dentine interaction is much more unknown. We suggest that the carious lesion and the defect in the Crown that result could be one of the mechanical stimulations that causes deposition of another layer of dentine. This could be modeled using finite element analysis

Figure 5 Strain energy density of only bone of the poor gradient of stiffness model

As the implant and abutment here have lower E than the crown, most of strain energy density lies in bone. We did not do more gradient. We can take more than two values of E and distribute them over crown, abutment and implant.

Figure 6 This is the displacement of model with poor gradient of stiffness

Total displacement/highest bone displacement $\approx 3.8/0.5 \approx 7.6$

Figure 7 This is the bone displacement of model with better gradient of stiffness

Figure 8 This is the strain energy density of model with better gradient of stiffness

Figure 9 train energy density of only bone of the poor gradient of stiffness model

Figure 10 This is the displacement of model of the natural tooth

Region A indicate clearly the center of rotation of tooth inside of its socket

Total displacement/highest bone displacement $\approx 24/5 \approx 4.8$

Total displacement / highest displacement in $\approx 24/ 50 \approx 0.5$ the PD

Figure 11 This is displacement of the tooth model where the tooth sub-domain had been hidden to facilitate comparison

Surprisingly the model of tooth revealed that the displacement at the region A is higher than at region B, which is opposite to what we had been seen in all models, even the reverse of the two pieces model. The regions of displacement (color bands) at the side of force application is lower than on the contralateral corresponding region. This could be better revealed by contour graph. That could indicate the bone remodeling is higher at the side of force application in contrast to all implant models. Region C is higher than region D. This pattern of strain, which give a clue for stresses

distribution, could be the reason for the change in the growth of the jaw when the implant is placed during active growth periods

Figure 12 This is displacement of the tooth model where the tooth and PD sub-domains had been hidden to facilitate comparison

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (N/m²)

Figure 13 Strain energy density of the tooth model

Figure 14 Strain energy density of the tooth model, but only the bone sub-model had been shown

This exaggeration in the displacement provides a cushion to the natural tissues and provides more displacement of components after came in contact with each other. Region A is not present in all implant models. As we concert with the bone, we had not analyzed the results that reveal the PD compartment. As we demonstrated previously, the ratio of displacement between the total displacement of implant and that occurring in the bone, which is different from the tooth model, this different ration could be a clue for the decreased proprioception in case of implant-supported Crown, Bridge or denture, in comparison to those supported by a natural tooth or teeth

References

References

1. *Effect of teeth periodontium presence on the bone physiology against stiffer status after implant placement or teeth ankylosis event. Teeth as jaw weakeners: a pivotal concept in the biomechanics.* Saadoon, M. Z. (. s.l. : International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), 1(2), 1–33., 2025).
2. *MOHAMMED BODIES' ANALYSIS FEA OF DENTAL IMPLANTS' DESIGN CRITERIA.* Saadoon, M. Z. (2020).

Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.